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Annotation: *In this article, the creative thinking of students in educational institutions, life skills, analytical skills and decision-making skills the role of modern education in development, as well as the basis for modern education advantages of calculated online education, independent education methods are described.*

Keywords: *modern education, skills, podcasts, e-books, q electronic education.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern education is taught in schools and educational institutions in the 21st century is the latest and most modern version of education. Modern education is not only Trade, focuses on well-known academic subjects of science and art, but also creative in students thinking, life skills, values education, analytical skills and decisionsqq aimed at developing reception skills. Modern education also to educate students and make the learning process more interesting and fun Mobile apps for YouTube, podcasts, e-books, movies, etc. are the latestq uses technologies. We are all in a teacher-centered classroom, with the teacher in front, the students education in a system where you sit in neat rows, listen to lectures and take notes we got To some extent, this system has been and is the core of our education system also constitutes Schools have relied on it for decades, and more recently faced changes.

Advantages of the modern education system

Distance education: You can study at any university. If you even if you can't go to the ground or pay, it's online for you from home allows to read. Every university also values distance education. Distance learning to choose any course that suits you and your profession will help.

Flexibility: You can learn from anywhere at any time you can, you don't have to go to campus. You at your own pace you can learn.

Student-centered: Online learning is student-centered. A student focuses more on the areas where he needs to improve and goes deep into them gives knowledge.

Low cost : No travel cost as you can study from home. No need to pay for classrooms and teachers.

Disadvantages of the modern education system Lack of social interaction: Online learning courses on their own courses. These students have relationships with their peers makes development difficult. Limited social interaction and face-to-face interaction no.

Potential for distraction: Less assertive and lacks self-motivation the possibility of distracting students is very high. Pupils their studies lose and do something else.

Pupils are isolated: Pupils have nothing to do with the outside world are out of touch, making the reader feel lonely and isolated creates a high chance.

Traditional education system

In traditional education, students are at a certain time and in a certain place collected under. The teaching method of traditional education is by the teacher managed. Students are peers to clear their doubts or the teacher after class to do the same communicate with The student's knowledge depends on the teacher's knowledge. Let's look at the advantages and disadvantages of traditional education.

Advantages of traditional education system

Temporary : Students for a specific time and break for each term they spend time. All this time is planned at the beginning, students follow this procedure and do them in a timely and disciplined manner.

Social interactions: Students interact with their peers helps them to build their character. They are they learn to share and respect others. Extracurricular activities: These students reveal their hidden talents gives others the opportunity to demonstrate. This is for their talent helps them to be recognized and excel in their lives.

Face-to-face communication: Students directly communicate with their teachers they can do. Questions and more in areas where they have doubts can give explanations.

Disadvantages of the traditional education system

Generalized education: Generalized education for all students makes it difficult for them to learn things that are interesting to them. Different students are different have different talents and interests that this general education cannot provide. Students spend more time and effort on studies they are not good at and it will not help them in their future careers.

Passive listeners: In traditional education, students listen to their teachers they should listen. Sometimes students don't try to listen to teachers. They are not interested in lectures and become passive listeners.

No Flexible Time: Traditional education is rigid and difficult to stud follows the schedule. Students have difficulty coping with this.

Cost: It is very expensive because the school has certain conditions provides and tuition fees for teachers, etc. Everyone is into it unable and ultimately unable to obtain credit.

Teacher-directed learning: Teacher and books are the main information are sources. Students are not able to learn new things and their knowledge is limited by books and knowledge given by teachers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the positive and negative sides of the education system there is According to the current conditions, the modern education system is different from the traditional education system better. In the modern education system, especially meaningful organization of the educational process it is advisable to use modern technical means. Including technology, information, computer, multimedia, internet, distance learning, unified information environment and similar information-communication the use of modern means of technology is effective giving.

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